

WHY YOU SHOULD BE INTERESTED IN TECHNOLOGY ROADMAPS FOR COMPOUND SEMICONDUCTORS

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Invited Abstract

Unlike the silicon semiconductor industry, the compound semiconductor industry does not have an international consensus for a few selected applications and markets to set priorities for investments. The main purpose of this paper is to increase the awareness among industrial decision-makers about the need for an international consensus or technology roadmap concerning selected compound semiconductors. Reasons are given for why there needs to be more wide-spread involvement in technology roadmaps for compound semiconductors. The technical challenges presented by predictive computer simulations, high performance analog-to-digital converters, and RF power devices are three areas from among many for which technology roadmaps would be appropriate.

I. Introduction and Motivation

A technology roadmap represents an industrial consensus with inputs from the research community and is often an effective technique to: 1) Reduce uncertainties in investments, 2) Use changes among technologies as opportunities for increased performance and functionality, 3) Increase the probability for more robust economic performance, 4) Guide critical research, and 5) Accelerate the rates of both technology development and deployment.[1,2] It is most effective when it serves to increase industrial cooperation and to produce positive changes in how companies work together. The very existence of roadmaps mentioning compound semiconductors, such as technology roadmaps from the National Electronics Manufacturing Initiative (NEMI),[3] Optoelectronics Industry Development Association (OIDA),[4] Microelectronics Advanced Research Initiative – Optoelectronics (MEL-ARI-OPTO),[5] and Optoelectronics Industry and Technology Development Association (OITDA),[6] means that decision-makers in the compound semiconductor industry have started to alter their attitudes, and thereby, to enable more cooperation.¹ However, much more remains to be accomplished in order to approach the benchmark established by the silicon complementary-metal-oxide-semiconductor (Si

¹ Certain commercial equipment, instruments, or materials are identified in this paper in order to specify adequately the experimental or theoretical procedures. Such identification does not imply recommendation by the National Institute of Standards and Technology, nor does it imply that the materials or equipment identified are necessarily the best available for the purpose.

CMOS) industry and its International Technology Roadmap for Semiconductors (ITRS).[7]

The field of compound semiconductors does not have an equivalent to standard CMOS technology. Standardization in compound semiconductors has not occurred nearly to the extent that standardization has occurred in silicon technology for the planar CMOS building block.[8] Compound semiconductor applications have to some degree been limited in the past to special applications. As a result, producers of compound semiconductor devices have adjusted their technologies to their customers' special applications more than they have driven a compound semiconductor technology and its market.

II. Trends in the Semiconductor Industry

The competitiveness among silicon CMOS manufacturers is shifting from an emphasis on technology and fabrication to a much greater emphasis on product design, architecture, algorithm, and software; that is, it is shifting from technology-oriented R&D to product-oriented R&D. Other trends are: 1) Increased costs for R&D and production facilities may become too great for any one company or country to accept; 2) Shorter process technology life cycles; 3) Emphasis on faster characterization of manufacturing processes; 4) All-global participants in the "Si CMOS ecosystem" now collaborate to develop and improve manufacturing technologies (e.g., ITRS and International SEMATECH; and 5) Many observers credit collaborative, consensus-based planning and deliberate road-mapping efforts for the sustained average annual growth rate of 15 % for the Si CMOS semiconductor industry over the last decade.

The digitization of almost everything and wireless (un-tethered) high data-rate telecommunication systems offer economic opportunities to merge compound semiconductor and silicon technologies. The Internet has accelerated the development and deployment of digital telecommunication systems.[8] Due to the ability of compound semiconductors to operate at frequencies higher than those that can be obtained with silicon technologies and also due to their superior optical properties, the compound semiconductor market is shifting from a niche market position to a new, more center stage position. Placing compound semiconductor and silicon devices on the same chip, package, or board now ties together more than before the successes of compound semiconductors and silicon semiconductors. This interdependence occurs in the field of telecommunication more than ever. A key challenge will be to have the pace of innovation in compound semiconductors proceed in “lock-step” with the pace of innovation in silicon semiconductors. For example, some believe that a way to reduce interconnect delay times is to co-integrate compound semiconductor and silicon devices.

III. Key Market Forces

Two key market forces are: 1) Market share dynamics among competing technologies and 2) The costs of doing business and maintaining its infrastructure becoming too great for one company or one country to assume. A shift that is similar to the shift in the silicon industry from technology-oriented R&D to product-oriented R&D may occur for one or two major applications of compound semiconductors; particularly, in applications for which compound semiconductors and silicon co-exist. Considering 1) This context of change, 2) Compound semiconductors as key enablers of larger markets that use Si CMOS, and 3) The success of consensus-based planning in the silicon CMOS industry, raises questions such as: 1) “How much value would an International Technology Roadmap for Compound Semiconductors (ITRCS) add?” 2) “Is our community ready to undertake the challenge of formulating an ITRCS?” 3) “Who will provide the necessary resources?” 4) “Could it become part of an expanded ITRS?” and 5) “What will be the interplay among commercial applications, available frequency spectrum, and RF device technology options for designing high-data rate telecommunication systems?” Figure 1 illustrates the interplay and options for this last question. Figure 1 is adapted from Fig. 1 of the paper by D. Barlas, et. al., Microwave Journal, page 22, June 1999 and is printed with permission from the Editor.

IV. Lessons Learned

Reviewing the histories of the ITRS and the NEMI Roadmaps is worthwhile for those becoming more involved with international roadmapping of compound semiconductors because such histories offer several lessons that are applicable to the compound semiconductor industry. These lessons include: 1) Prior to the mid 1980s, most Si CMOS companies assumed that over 50 % of what they knew was proprietary and not to be part of consensus-based planning and collaborations; 2) From the late 1980s to today, most Si CMOS companies found that over 50 % of what they know is not proprietary and may be shared with other companies for a globally more competitive industry; 3) Many technology barriers, once thought to be of concern to a few companies, are common throughout the industry (Overcoming such barriers offers an appropriate focus for technology roadmaps.); and 4) The challenge is to have a large enough effort to be effective, but still focused enough to have measurable progress.

Interplay Among Commercial Applications, Frequency, and RF Device Technology Today's Technology Options for Designers

What will the technology options be in 2005 or 2010?

Figure 1

V. Existing Roadmaps

Segments of the compound semiconductor industry have contributed to some technology roadmaps that deal, in part, with selected challenges for their industry. However, these roadmaps tend to be fragmented efforts as far as compound semiconductors are concerned and lack the details for infrastructure building that would be comparable to those in the ITRS for Si CMOS. From the historical perspective, the ongoing road-mapping activities in the United States (NEMI [3] and OIDA [4]), Europe (MEL-ARI-OPTO [5]), and Japan (OITDA [6]) may signify, as did the early planning efforts in the 1980s for silicon CMOS, that now is the time for more

global road-mapping efforts concerning selected applications of compound semiconductors.

VI. Candidates for Roadmaps

There are many potential candidate areas that could be part of an ITRCS. We mention here for illustrative purposes the areas of physical models for device simulators, analog-to-digital converters (ADCs), and RF (radio frequency) power amplifiers.

A. Physical Models for Devices

Both the ITRS and NEMI roadmaps have sections on modeling and simulation needs. One common theme in both roadmaps is the need for predictive computer simulations of devices. A key to predictive simulations is to have more physically correct models. Figure 2 is one example of more physically correct models for minority electron mobilities in GaAlAs heterojunction bipolar transistors (HBTs), where $x=0.0$ and 0.3 for the topmost and bottommost curves, respectively.[9] A roadmap on computer device simulators could assist commercial software vendors to provide the best possible physical models in device simulators.

Figure 2

B. Analog-to-Digital Converters

Wireless, real-time digital video (WRTDV) systems (e.g., mobile video phones, electronic notebooks, electronic cinema, and mobile-un-tethered internet appliances with very high data rates) could provide the necessary focus for an ITRCS. Digital video in the context of this paper is much broader than its usual meaning. Digital video, as used here, means very high quality and very high bit rates of digital data or information (video, audio, computer, and other forms of

digital information) that are processed in real-time. Technology gaps could be ranked, if possible, according to the perceived technical difficulty and market or economic opportunity. Examples of technology gaps include (in no particular order): 1) Miniaturization of microwave filters; 2) Very linear RF amplifiers; 3) High frequency RF power amplifiers – GaAs and LDMOS competition; 4) Circuits with large numbers of HBTs and resonant tunneling diodes (RTDs) for high-speed and high-bit resolution ADCs; 5) Long-lived, continuous semiconductor lasers; and 6) Smart, adaptive error correcting circuits for digital receivers.

The adoption of high definition television (HDTV) and enhanced digital services will exacerbate spectrum crowding and increase the public's awareness of today's technical limitations of the hardware and software that are used to deal with multipath and error correction in receivers. Spectrum crowding may be alleviated by either adding more channels, which means usually higher operating frequencies, or by designing power amplifiers that are very linear. Both going to higher frequencies and using very linear circuits tend to favor III-V compound semiconductors over group IV semiconductors. Economics and technical performance will determine the respective roles for compound and silicon semiconductors in alleviating spectrum crowding.

The data in Figure 3, adapted from Figure 1 in Ref.[10], show a significant challenge for all semiconductors – III-Vs, Si, and SiGe; namely, ADCs may not be able to deliver the high quality digital data (video, audio, computer, and multimedia) for market acceptance. This empirical data on the number of bits (resolution) vs. sampling rates show that a boundary - the solid line in Figure 3 - exists in the performance of ADCs. This solid line is several orders of magnitude away from the Heisenberg uncertainty limit for ADCs and is moving at a given sampling frequency towards higher bit resolutions at the rate of about 1.5 bits every 8 years or so. This motion is too slow for those communication markets that depend on high performance. The star indicates the ADC performance that is needed today for all-digital receivers, but such performance will not be available for 22 years at the current rate of evolution. This is a "red" brick wall in the ITRS sense.

The ADC performance-boundary limits the headroom in which digital processing can handle adequately in real-time encoding/decoding and error correcting to increase functionality. One example is the functionality that is needed due to multipath and adjacent channel interferences. A technology roadmap could reduce the

time to reach the star in Figure 3 and thereby to implement digital linearization of base-station transmitters.

Analog-to-Digital Converter Technology

Figure 3

C. RF Power

Loss of CMOS market share by U.S. companies motivated them to collaborate more on infrastructure in the early 1980s. This led to today's ITRS. Likewise, more recently, GaAs devices for powers greater than 10W lost market share to silicon laterally diffused MOS (LDMOS) as LDMOS became the technology of choice for cellular base stations below 2 GHz. But, with the advent of third generation (3G) cellular communications, RF high power GaAs technologies are beginning to enter the mainstream of wireless communications networks. The competition between GaAs and LDMOS for RF power base station applications is clearly seen in 3G applications. Comprehensive roadmaps must deliver 15% to 20% price reductions per year to meet customer expectations and to have GaAs become more competitive with LDMOS for 3G frequency applications.[11]

VII. Conclusions

To deliver its full potential and to ensure its continued success, the compound semiconductor industry needs improved global cooperation from everyone (industry, academia, and governments) to address the tough technical challenges on the road ahead. We have established a Web-site at <http://www.eeel.nist.gov/812/itrcs.html> for collecting and discussing ideas, comments, and questions relating to the possible creation of an ITRCS. The value added

by an international technology roadmap for compound semiconductors (ITRCS) will depend on how industry leaders respond. In summary, you should become more involved because "No one is big enough to drive the totality of the infrastructure and pre-competitive investments on their own," Avtar Oberai, a founding director of SEMATECH.[2]

Acknowledgments

The author thanks his colleagues throughout the world for numerous discussions and helpful comments, particularly, those colleagues in Asia, Australia, Europe, and North America, some of whom are cited in this paper. He acknowledges the continued support from NIST.

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